

Old Wine in New Bottle: Brainstorming and Inquiry Approaches Fulfilling Present Day Secondary Schools' Students' Educational Needs

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 21, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 22, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Brainstorming, Educational Needs, Inquiry, Secondary Level</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6685665</p>	<p><i>Educational improvement and individual's learning have been remaining crown goals of educationists for the states. Teachers are the nation builders of societies which act as appetizer in enhancing students' social, economical, political and educational needs. Teachers' instructional strategies make students active and self-motivated to illuminate the concept of right and wrong for educational revolution. The present quantitative ex-post-facto research leading to positivist paradigm research was conducted to gauge the effect of teachers' instructional strategies used to accomplish learners' educational needs on a sample of 10th grade 2,700 respondents randomly selected from the public sector secondary schools of Lahore Division of Pakistan. After ensuring content validity from experts and Cronbach's Alpha reliability statistics .845, the authors administered a self-constructed questionnaire to collect data from participants. After ensuring students' enrollment during data collection, the researchers obtained students' educational achievements/needs from the Board of Intermediate and Secondary Education, Lahore. The authors applied normality statistics; Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, $n > 2000$, $p < .05$ to ensure appropriate statistics on the data. The results of regression analysis revealed that overall teachers' pedagogical practices were fulfilling 49.90% students' educational needs whereas, brainstorming 46.20% and inquiry 34.50% were fulfilling secondary schools' students' educational needs. On the basis of the results, it is recommended that Pakistani teachers' training institutions may emphasis on modern instructional strategies focusing students-centered and teacher-centered techniques as stated in National Curriculum document to fulfill students' educational need.</i></p>

Introduction

Teaching is a multifaceted process that helps teachers to share ideas and concepts among students. It is a medium of transferring knowledge, values and concepts to bring positive change in students' behavior. It facilitates learning process (Mang & Mankilik, 2002) through conducting instructional strategies for students' learning (Damar et al., 2016). Leading purpose of successful teaching is to fulfill students' educational needs. Teaching process is carried by a remarkable personalities; teacher who motivate students by using instructional strategies (Adu-Boateng & Goodnough, 2022; Moore, 2014; Umer & Siddiqui, 2013), brainstorming (Maier et al., 2022) and inquiry (Anupam, 2022; Toma, 2022; Wang et al., 2022) in classrooms to satisfy students' educational needs.

Brainstorming is an instructional strategy that provokes students' creative and problem solving skills (Al-Khatib, 2012) to make them innovative and ignite students' minds towards logical reasoning and understanding (Jarwan, 2005; Odoh, 2013). Teachers treat with students in classrooms using brainstorming strategy for conceptual understanding to attain remarkable achievement scores (Al-Shammari, 2015; Sabet & Ghorbanpour, 2014). Brainstorming arouses students' devotions towards learning, produces different ideas regarding concerned topics and develops multiple logical concepts to resolve ambiguous problems (Hryrfrsh & Sadeghi, 2010). Brainstorming strategy revolve round five stages: a) *beginning rule*; teachers inform to follow entire criteria while writing on board and students are bound to follow it, b) *statement of the problem/issue*; teachers choose an attention arousing problem, having no unambiguous material in textbook, then state it among students. Problem demands students' prior knowledge and maximum solutions, c) *interpretation of thoughts*; teachers' debate enriched person to person discussion ensuring every ones participation on prescribed problem, d) *confirm thought for blending and perfection*; teachers confirm one innovative thought, purify it and discard others and; e) *evaluation of thought*: is the stage to finalize group/individual thought towards closing end towards radical-us direction (Rizi et al., 2013). Brainstorming inserts considerable effects on learners in term of: sufficient imagination, creation of thoughts by justification, amplification and argumentation on ideas and permit learners to contribute in conversation to build capabilities in account of critical thinking by instructing &

supporting (Filgona et al., 2016). Teachers apply this strategy among learners to develop novelty of thoughts to solve problematic concerns of contemporary era (Edelman et al., 2022; Hryrfrosh & Sadeghi, 2010).

Brainstorming is used to obtain students better educational needs (Kosalge et al., 2022). Plethora of literature reported that brainstorming is an important creative technique that is frequently used by the teachers to solve problems, generate ideas, and to come up with creative solutions to problems (Chaijum, 2020). Teachers apply brainstorming to encourage students' thoughts and ideas for creative solutions of the problems (Wible, 2020). It also helps to get students unstuck by "shocking" them out from their traditional ways of thinking (Morganna et al., 2020). The researchers make significant contributions in exploring the effect of brainstorming on students' educational needs (Al-Samarraie & Hurmuzan, 2018; Filgona et al., 2016). Odoh (2013) planned quasi-experimental study to find out the impact of brainstorming on students' educational needs on a sample of randomly selected 156 respondents. Findings revealed significant difference between brainstorming lecture and students' educational needs, $t(154) = 14.61, p < .05$; students of brainstorming obtained better educational needs ($M = 68.23$) as compared to students from lecture ($M = 45.97$), significant difference was yielded between students' gender, $t(154) = 14.68, p < .05$; male students had better educational needs, ($M = 72.21$) as compared to female students ($M = 61.56$). Rizi et al., (2013) structured quantitative study to measure the influence of brainstorming on students' educational needs on a sample of 61 participants applying cluster sampling technique. The researchers collected data through administering self-constructed achievement test based on 20-items focusing students' cognitive level; knowledge, evaluation and combination. The researchers validated self-constructed questionnaire from the experts and piloted to confirm Cronbach's alpha reliability statistics .793. The results of independent samples t-test showed significant difference between brainstorming, lecture method and students' educational needs, $t(58) = 14.13, p < .01$; students of brainstorming were better ($M = 14.83, SD = 3.17$) as compared to students of lecture method ($M = 13.13, SD = 3.94$). Filgona et al. (2016) planned quantitative study to find out influence of brainstorming on students' educational gains on a sample of 213 respondents. After ensuring validity from psychological experts and Cronbach's Alpha reliability statistics; .721, the researchers administered a self-constructed questionnaire to collect data from respondents. The findings of independent samples t-test revealed significant difference between brainstorming and lecture method and students' educational needs, $t(201) = 6.331, p < .01$. Students of brainstorming gained better educational needs ($M = 49.6, SD = 20.426$) as compared to students from lecture method ($M = 31.484, SD = 20.507$). Malkawi and Smadi (2018) gauged the effect of brainstorming on students' educational needs. The results established no significant difference between brainstorming, lecture method students' educational needs, ($F(2, 115) = 3.618, p > .01$); significant difference was present between brainstorming, lecture method and students' educational needs, $t(232) = 2.773, p < .01$; students of brainstorming were better ($M = 27.00, SD = 6.729$) as compared from the students of lecture method ($M = 23.567, SD = 6.754$).

Contemporary era is considered as era of science and technology. Scientific innovations are spreading rapidly by mutual collaboration of education. Percentage of scientific education is enhanced by applying different instructional methods during teaching-learning. Among them inquiry supports on process focus, exploring, group learning, discussion monitoring and the teachers in real-life applications (Anupam, 2022; Cairns & Areepattamannil, 2019; Fitzgerald et al., 2019). Inquiry is student-centered approach in which teachers guide and direct the students through questions posed, method design and techniques in data interpretations (Toma, 2022). Resultantly, the students actively find out information to sustain their inquiries that put noteworthy effects on the progress of states (Abdi, 2014; Karamustafaoglu, 2010). Inquiry collects facts through exploring individuals' special involvement in currently happening phenomenon (Shamsudin et al., 2013). The process of inquiry consists of explorations of problem, search its reality through serious consideration, start examining, raise queries, perform experimentation and interpret results and thought unconsciously about its uniqueness (Shamsudin et al., 2013; Pedaste et al., 2015). Teachers act as catalyst during whole inquiry process to strengthen teaching learning process (Kang & Keinonen, 2018; Martin-Hansen, 2002; Pedaste et al., 2015). Students feel free to talk and argue with peers to shape inquiry cycle towards reaching conclusions (Sadeh & Zion, 2012). Students raise queries, carry out exploration and conduct activities based on their curiosity of inquiry (Martin-Hansen, 2002). Students and teachers follow parameters of inquiry to explore the phenomenon, investigate constructed questions and find solutions of the problems (Jiang & McComas, 2015; Koksai & Berberoglu, 2012). Inquiry is categorized in *teacher-centered*, *students-centered* and *guided inquiry* (National Research Council, 2000; Kang & Keinonen, 2018). In *teacher-centered inquiry* students are bound to explore already constructed questions for real investigations. In this process, the students not only have options to bound teachers' hypothesis but also talk freely and argue with peers to shape inquiry cycle towards closing end (Sadeh & Zion, 2012). *Student-centered inquiry* is complicated type as it starts from raising students' queries, carry out exploration and conduct activities for supporting their curiosity level (Martin-Hansen, 2002). *Guided inquiry* allows students and teachers to follow parameters to find authentic solution of the valid problems. It is used to encourage students' learning through exploration and investigations (Jiang & McComas, 2015). It is apparent that guided inquiry consequent from prearranged inquiry to open inquiry (Koksai & Berberoglu, 2012) and inserts note-worthy influence on students' educational needs (Arnold et al., 2014; Herranen et al., 2019).

Inquiry put imperative effect at every grade level (Cuevas et al., 2005). Instructions imparted through inquiry escort students towards positive educational inspiration and arouse abilities towards better educational needs (Berg et al., 2003). Maxwell et al., (2015) framed quantitative research to explore the effect of inquiry on students' educational need in Georgia State of USA on sample of conveniently selected 42 students administering *Physical Science Knowledge Assessment* and *Survey of Science Attitude and Students Classroom Engagement Checklist*. The results of independent samples t-test showed significant difference between inquiry and conventional method on students' educational needs, $t(40) = 9.11, p < .01$; students of inquiry were better ($M = 51.14, SD = 14.01$) as compared to students of conventional method ($M = 50.65, SD = 15.02$). Ifeanyi-Uche and Chima (2013) structured quantitative research to find out the influence of inquiry on students' educational needs on a sample of randomly selected 80 students administering *Home economics Achievement Test*. The results of independent samples t-test declared significant difference between inquiry and conventional teaching on students' educational needs, $t(78) = 1.96, p < .01$; students of inquiry were better in fulfilling their educational needs ($M = 53.5, SD = 9.54$) as compared to students of conventional teaching ($M = 25.3, SD = 4.23$). Abdi (2014) conducted quantitative study to explore the influence of inquiry on students' educational needs on sample of purposively selected 40 students administering *Academic Achievement Test*. The findings revealed no significant difference between inquiry and lecture method on students' educational needs; students of inquiry have about same educational gains ($M = 3.15, SD = 1.461$) as compared to lecture method ($M = 2.95, SD = 1.538$).

Students' Educational Needs; SEN are the reflection of students' cognitive abilities. They are teachers' use of methods, effectiveness and mirror of students' cognitive abilities. Achievement scores are the information demonstrated by students for effective learning (Issa et al., 2012). They are students' obtained knowledge and developed abilities in a school. It is considered as indicator of students' academic success, students' performance and instructional objectives (Shepherd et al., 2006). Teachers' concentrate on their teaching methods to obtain students' educational needs (Kalaian & Kasim, 2014; Nwagbo, 2001). Secondary schools' students are more inclined towards educational needs. Teachers and students build trust on each other through strong communication (Amina, 2016; Pinxten et al., 2010). Students' educational needs are 10th grade annual examination conducted by Board of Intermediate and Secondary Education; BISE of concerned divisions. There are working nine Boards of Intermediate and Secondary Education; BISE under command of Punjab province of Pakistan. Every board is responsible to conduct exams at the end of academic year May-June. Throughout a year, secondary schools' teachers invest their educational, spiritual, experiential and social potential in arousing students' educational needs. Enrolled students appeared in exams and according to set pattern board conduct exams then arrange paper marking schedules. After hectic processes, Boards announced results that is actual Students' Educational Needs; *SEN*.

Statement of the Problem

Teachers invest their maximum personal and professional potentials to sparkle students' talent and hidden abilities in obtaining educational demands (Felder, 2011; Handelsman et al., 2005). In this regard, Government structured curriculum focusing standardized guidelines to provide contemporary education. Educational policies are formed to cope students' present day educational needs. On the other hand, Pakistani teachers are less portraying their pedagogical skills with true spirit and vigor. Resultantly, the level of students' educational needs is reducing day-by-day (Hassan et al., 2021; Hassan & Akbar, 2020). This decline level is due to the continuous usage of teachers' traditional strategies. Moreover, the school is a platform where teachers implement students-centered (Bennett, 2022; Claramita et al., 2022; Wang, 2011; Wright, 2011) and teachers-centered instructional strategies (Emaliana, 2017; Mascolo, 2009). The applications of instructional strategies are important indicators that significantly enhance students' educational needs (Ahmad et al., 2022; Salleh et al., 2022) in educational institutions. There seems also carelessness of head teachers' lack of interest and overloaded the teachers with personal and irrelevant tasks that are producing severe hurdles in implementing instructional strategies (Nawaz, 2020). Ending in a debate, students are directly affected from this negligence that destroy the students' cognitive potential and buried their hidden potentials. On the other hand, Government construct national curriculum, conduct teachers training and invest billion of rupees to make teachers academically, socially and professionally strong. There exist a gap between Government strategies and implementation of documented realities. This research is an attempt that to, what extent the applications of instructional strategies are fulfilling current-day students' educational needs. The authors are anxiously wanted to find out the actual use of brainstorming and inquiry approaches are playing significant effect on students' educational needs. The researchers are eager to figure out students' current alarming situations which lead them towards slackness.

Research Questions

The authors structure following research questions in the research

1. To what extent brainstorming effect on present-day students' educational needs?
2. Is there any effect of inquiry on present-day students' educational needs?

Research Design and Methodology

The root of this part is linked with teachers' instructional strategies used in classrooms with respect to research design, methodology and instruments. Secondary schools' teachers used their instructional approaches for the sake of students' maximum educational needs. The current part includes explanation of procedures that spectacles the effect of teachers' brainstorming and inquiry on students' educational needs.

Population and Sample of the Research

The population is the group of interest to whom the researcher(s) generalize the results of a research. The population is a group of individuals, objects, or items from which the sample is selected for measurement (Singh, 2007; Fraenkel & Wallen, 2009). The larger group to which the researcher(s) apply the results is considered the population of the research (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2003; Orodho, 2005). Population includes the people or items with the characteristics that one wishes to study (Link et al., 2008; Gay et al., 2006; Fraenkel et al., 2012). The population of the current research consisted of 57,350 students; male 24,353 and females 32,997 from 383 high schools of district Lahore, Punjab-Pakistan. The sample of the research consisted of 2,700 secondary level students, randomly selected through applying Yamane (1967) and Cochran (1977) sample size calculating formula, as cited in other researches (Bartlett et al., 2001; Dell et al., 2002; Woolson et al., 1986).

Data Collection Instruments

After review of literature, meetings with the experts and classrooms' observations, the researchers self-developed a questionnaire for students regarding teachers' brainstorming and inquiry used in classrooms. Self-structured questionnaire is used to obtain information from respondents focusing cover anonymity and avoiding biases of researchers especially when topic is sensitive in nature. It spotlights according to respondents' cognitive level and cultural variations having less chance of measuring inaccuracies. It is low cost and incorporates significant preventions during typing and formatting errors (Bifulco et al., 2005; Bird, 2009; Edwards, 2010; Goodman, 1997; Kazi & Khalid, 2012; Lavrakas, 2008; Zouwen, 2000). The authors constructed items of the questionnaire focusing on 10th grade students' understandings level. The researchers used Likert type options of questionnaire to measure respondents' views. Likert type responses are the best way to measure participants' sight regarding any construct (Cohen et al., 2011). Items of the questionnaire were mode of Likert type responses ranges from 1= never, 2 = rarely, 3 = sometimes, 4 = often and 5 = always already used in other studies (Vagias, 2006; Hassan, 2020). The researchers measured the validity and reliability of questionnaire to enhance the accuracy of research work. Validity of instrument used for the correctness, meaningfulness and usefulness of results (Tavakol & Denick, 2011; Twycross & Shields, 2004) and measures the truth or falsity of obtained data (Burns & Grove, 2005). To confirm the preferred items, the researchers consulted with relevant experts to ensure the content validity of the instruments. Final questionnaire consist of 10-items: brainstorming = 4 items and inquiry = 6 items mode of 5-point Likert type responses. After ensuring validity, the researchers piloted a self-constructed questionnaire to ensure Cronbach's Alpha reliability statistics. A pilot study is the pivotal element of excellent research design. Pilot study refers to pre-study or miniature version of full scale study. It provides insight about future research hurdle. Literature reveals that 10 to 30% sample of respondents is appropriate for pilot study from projected sample size (Hill, 1998; Julious, 2005; Connelly, 2008; Hertzog, 2008; Johanson & Brooks, 2010; Van Belle, 2011). The researchers selected 10% sample for pilot study from actual study sample for projection. For piloting, the authors personally visited the schools, ensured ethical considerations, and handed over the questionnaire among secondary schools' students. The authors collected the data from the students as they are best observers about their teachers' classroom observations (Hassan & Akbar, 2020; Murtaza & Akbar, 2019; Zouwen, 2000). After collecting the data, the authors entered in SPSS to calculate Cronbach's Alpha reliability score. Reliability of questionnaire employs to measure the consistency of scores by calculating Cronbach's Alpha scores (Cohen et al., 2018; Fraenkel et al., 2012; Heale & Twycross, 2015; Ruiz et al., 2022). After collecting the data, the researchers entered in SPSS to calculate reliability score. Cronbach's Alpha score of brainstorming was .848, inquiry was .854, respectively.

Data Collection Procedures

After ensuring Cronbach's Alpha scores, the researchers selected addresses from School Education Department; SED, obtained contact numbers and made phone calls to the heads of the institutions, told the purpose of the research. On prescribed schedule, the researchers visited schools, met with head of the institution and teachers, showed consent letter and explained the purpose of the study. The researchers satisfied head teachers and secondary schools' teachers by keeping in view the ethical considerations. They assured participants' informed consent, voluntary participation, confidentiality, anonymity and risk of harm both in physical and psychological as result of their participation (Bhutta, 2004; DeCosta et al., 2004; Kass et al., 2005; Marshall, 2007; Beebe & Smith, 2008; Jegede, 2009; Bull & Lindegger, 2011; Lo, 2012). The researchers personally discussed questionnaires with each respondent, guided and motivated the teachers for providing accurate information and administered the questionnaires to the respondents to get fill in. They stayed with respondents for discussion and guidance throughout process of filling questionnaires. They noted time taken by respondents to fill the questionnaire. In this way, the researchers collected the filled questionnaires from the students. Students were motivated for providing relevant data. The researchers satisfied queries rose during filling the questionnaires and stayed for discussion and guidance with respondents. Cooperation of the

respondents was highly appreciated. The researchers himself entered entire collected data in SPSS to ensure data analysis.

Research Results

The authors analyzed the data applying linear regression techniques to measure the effect of inquiry and brainstorming on used to enhance students' educational needs. There was no auto-correlation in data. Authenticity of the data were ensured through applying Durbon-Watson test, value ranged between 0-4 (Cronk, 2012; Montgomery et al., 2001).

Table 1 Overall Effect of Teachers Instructional Strategies on Present-day Students' Educational Needs

No	Variables	B	SE	β	t	p	Durbin-Watson
1	SEN (Constant)	432.815	.443		977.881	.01	1.032
	Variables	.422	.007	.707	59.882	.01	

Note: $R = .707^a$, $R^2 = .499$; ($F(1, 2,699) = 3585.82$, $p = .05^a$)

As delineated in Table 1, simple regression was conducted to measure the effect of brainstorming on students' educational needs with construction of significant regression equation ($F(1, 3599) = 3585.82$, $p < .01$) having .499 value of R^2 with 49.90% explained variations were observed with standardized regression co-efficient ($\beta = .707$). Centering the results of regression co-efficient output of independent samples t-test ascertained that teachers' instructional strategies were significant predictor on SEN, $t(3998) = 3585.82$, $p < .05$. Learners' estimated educational needs were equal to 432.815+.422 scores where teachers' usage of instructional strategies were evaluated teachers' pedagogical potential applied in the classrooms. It is concluded that students' educational needs were raised .422 points after applying teachers' teaching approaches to fulfill students' educational needs. In addition, the value of *Durbin-Watson* revealed that data were not auto-correlated

Table 2 Effect of Brainstorming on Present-day Students' Educational Needs

No	Variables	B	SE	β	t	p	Durbin-Watson
1	SEN (Constant)	428.617	.485		883.970	.05	1.678
	Brainstorming	1.648	.034	.680	48.128	.05	

Note: $R = .680^a$, $R^2 = .462$; ($F(1, 2699) = 2316.275$, $p = .05^a$)

As revealed in Table 2, the authors applied simple regression to measure that to what extent brainstorming fulfill students' educational needs. The interpretation reveals formation of significant regression equation ($F(1, 2699) = 2316.275$, $p < .01$) having .462 value of R^2 with 46.20% explained variations are observed with standardized regression co-efficient ($\beta = .680$). Focusing the results of regression co-efficient, the output of an independent samples t-test established that brainstorming was significant predictor on students' educational needs, $t(2698) = 48.128$, $p < .05$. Secondary schools' students' estimated educational needs were equal to 428.617+1.648 points whereas, the application of brainstorming was calculated through applying teachers' teaching potential used in classrooms. It is concluded that brainstorming is fulfilling 1.648 points secondary schools' students' educational needs. Further, the value of *Durbin-Watson* ensures that there was no auto-correlation in the data.

Table 3 Effect of Inquiry on Present-day Students' Educational Needs

No	Variables	B	SE	β	t	p	Durbin-Watson
1	SEN (Constant)	425.232	.526		808.635	.05	1.943
	Inquiry	.991	.026	.588	37.729	.05	

Note: $R = .588^a$, $R^2 = .345$; ($F(1, 2,699) = 1423.468$, $p = .05^a$)

As declared in Table 3, the authors run simple regression to measure the effect of inquiry on students' educational needs. An interpretation declared the structuring of significant regression equation ($F(1, 2699) = 1423.468$, $p < .01$) having .345 value of R^2 with 34.50% explained variations were seen with standardized regression co-efficient ($\beta = .588$). Centering the output of regression co-efficient, the results of an independent samples t-test ascertained that inquiry was a significant predictor on students' educational needs, $t(2698) = 37.729$, $p < .05$. Learners' estimated educational needs were equal to 425.232+.991 points whereas the application of inquiry was calculated through teachers' pedagogical potential applied in classrooms. It is concluded that students' educational needs were fulfilled .991 points after applying teachers' inquiry in classrooms. Moreover, the value of *Durbin-Watson* revealed that the data were not auto-correlated.

Discussion

Education develops wisdom among human beings that collectively affects on communities to make them conscious for educational revolution. Teachers implement innovative techniques; brainstorming and inquiry to make students more educated. Brainstorming strategy arouses students' innovative thoughts, constructs eagerness towards acquiring knowledge and strengthens their classroom involvement (Malkawi & Smadi, 2018; Kittami, 2001; Filgona et al., 2016; Mohammad, 2016). Notion brainstorming is the integration of stress-free and untailored strategy applies to reinforce students' problem solving, critical thinking and better educational outcomes (Kittami, 2001). The results of the current research established that 46.50% brainstorming

enhanced secondary schools' students' educational needs that support with results of others researches (Filgona et al., 2016; Odoh, 2013) whose findings revealed that brainstorming is an effective approach that put significant effect on students' cognitive abilities and educational needs. The findings of the current research established that teachers make continuous use of brainstorming enable students to take initiatives towards correct judgments and resolve complex community matters that also congruent with the results of other researches (Al-Samarraie & Hurmuzan, 2018; Malkawi et al., 2018). Brainstorming applied to count astonishing improvement of contemporary era learners' logical and innovative thinking abilities that enable students to take initiatives towards correct judgments and resolve complex educational matters. Moreover, the results of current research align with the finding of other studies (Aghazadeh, 2005; Al-Khatib, 2012; Al-maghawry, 2012; Jarwan, 2005; Mohammad, 2016; Rizi et al., 2013) whose findings established that teachers use brainstorming strategy to retain and promote actual facts and students' knowledge towards constructive way.

Inquiry arouses students' curiosity towards realm of intellectualities and topic understandings. Pivotal aim of inquiry is to develop abilities in students that enable them towards construction of essential concepts then express their entrenched misunderstandings (Santrock, 2001). Inquiry is based on exploration, formulation of theory and conduct experiments. This method makes students active thinkers and information seeker (Miller, 2014). Teachers reproduce mixture of developing strategies to make effective teaching learning process for the sake of students' outstanding educational achievements. Teachers apply inquiry to make students' learning productive during performing activities as an active contributor (Wang & Lin, 2008). Teachers focuses on hand on activities, cooperate with every student and works as a catalyst (Llewellyn, 2002; Wall et al., 2009). Inquiry replaces conventional instructional approaches; lecturing, talk and chalk method and permanent handling of textbook. Teachers engaged students to perform hands on activities based on their potentials and prepare students for further investigations and build up solid rationale to focus on interpretations of fact based results (Secker, 2002; Abdi, 2014). The findings of the current research reveal that secondary schools were applying 34.50% inquiry to fulfill students' educational needs that align with the finding of other studies (Ifeanyi-Unche & Chima, 2013; Maxwell et al., 2015). Moreover, during inquiry teaching, the teachers arouse students constructive thoughts that 1st time these considerations mismatched as per actual situations. Consideration behind this approach focuses individual's inspirations towards constructive solutions of burning issue and built association between issues and learning process (Koksai & Berberoglu, 2012). It is one of the facts that inquiry put note-worthy influence on students' educational needs (Arnold et al., 2014; Sadeh & Zion, 2012). Inquiry creates constructive attitudes and engages students in classrooms' activities as compared to those who taught through conventional teaching. The findings of the current research also support with the findings of other studies (Crawford, 2007; Huziak-Clark et al., 2007; Miller, 2014; Smolska & Taylor, 2004; Wolf & Fraser, 2008).

Conclusions

Education illuminates the concept of right and wrong between humans to make them educated. Complete improvement and individual's learning have been remaining crown goals of developed education system. Teachers use instructional strategies to polish students' hidden potential and enhance better success. The current research was an effort that to what extent Pakistani secondary schools' teachers are using brainstorming and inquiry to enhance students' educational needs. Brainstorming means using one's cognitive skills to resolve problems and to develop innovative solution of that burning dilemma in limited span of time. This essential strategy used to inflame students' hidden potentials in the education. Brainstorming strengthens students' relations and intellectual abilities which revolve around formation of thought provoking directions towards successful mode of required achievements. Inquiry stimulates students' knowledge construction from direct revelation of information and evidences. Teachers act as appetizer towards exploration of universe, discovery of facts, reflection, thinking and critical analysis. Focusing the worth of brainstorming and inquiry, the authors framed a research on a sample of 2,700 students, randomly selected from district Lahore, Punjab-Pakistan. After comprehensive review of literature, classrooms' observations and meetings with experts, the authors administered a self-constructed questionnaire among the respondents. The validity and Cronbach's Alpha reliability of the instrument were ensured. After ensuring normality of the data, the results of regression analysis established that overall teachers were making 50.10% less use of instructional strategies. Moreover, the use of brainstorming was 53.10% less and inquiry was 65.50% fewer among secondary schools students. It is evident that after facing diversity of problems; low pay, poor schools' infrastructure, head teachers' autocratic attitudes, departments' extra workload, scarcity of instructional materials, lack of staff, parents' poor concerns and, poverty allegation, the Pakistani teachers are still indulged in curricular and co-curricular activities. Implementation of national curriculum document and teachers' subject base training is also a weak aspect that significantly create hurdle in fulfilling students' educational needs. Based on the results of the research, the researchers recommended that Government of Punjab ensured the implementation of national curriculum document and arrange in-service teachers' training workshops focusing innovative instructional approaches that obviously fulfill present day students' educational needs. It is also recommended that both teachers and students

may be awarded good rewards which attract talent, increase productivity, reduce stress of employees, enhance proactive spirit, boosts moral values, develop skills and build institutions of good reputation.

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